

Transport Number of Acids in Aqueous Solutions. Part I. Nitric Acid

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Results from the determination of the cation-transport number of nitric acid in aqueous solution at various temperatures and concentrations indicate that the transport number varies directly as the square root of concentration up to 0.0886*M*. The logarithm of the transport number ratio of the cation and anion, i.e., $\log t_+^0/t_-^0$, appears to be related to the absolute temperature, *T*, by the equation:

$$\log t_+^0/t_-^0 = A + B/T$$

where *A* and *B* are constants for different acids.

Very little work appears to have been done on the cationic transport number of nitric acid. Although some workers¹⁻⁵ have made some contributions in this field, not much attention, however, seems to have been paid to the study of the variation of the transport number with concentration and temperature. The present investigation is an attempt to study this aspect of the problem in nitric acid with a newer technique used by Kerker *et al.*⁶

EXPERIMENTAL

The transport cell used was very much similar to that used by Kerker *et al.*⁶ and consisted of a silver anode and a platinum cathode. The graduations of the cell were checked with redistilled mercury. The strength of the potassium nitrate solution, used in the experiments, was as near as possible to the region given by Kohlrausch's regulating function, namely,

$$\frac{t_+}{C_1} = \frac{t_{k_+}}{C_2} \quad (1)$$

where t_+ and t_{k_+} represent the cationic transport numbers of nitric acid and potassium nitrate at their respective concentrations, C_1 and C_2 .

In order to determine the cationic transport number, the nitric acid solution of desired concentration with methyl orange indicator (0.002% to 0.004%) was filled in the graduated limb of the cell and the platinum electrode was fitted in position. The potassium

1. Bein, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 27, 1.
2. Jahn, *ibid.*, 1901, 37, 673.
3. Dennison and Steele, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1909, 5, 165.
4. Stonehill, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 647.
5. Cavington and Prue, *ibid.*, 1957, 1567.
6. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, 56, 1039; 1961, 57, 781.

nitrate solution, made from dried A.R. grade KNO_3 and conforming to the conditions laid down in equation (1) above, was filled in the other limb and the silver anode was fitted in position. The electrical connections were suitably made.

The electric current was supplied from a set of 90-volts dry cells and the voltage readings were taken at intervals of two minutes against a 100-ohm resistance on a Pye-potentiometer. Movements of the boundary were noted at various intervals with the help of a magnifying glass. All experiments were performed in a thermostat with an accuracy of $\pm 0.01^\circ$.

The current drop in the course of experiments was plotted against time and the resulting curve was integrated to find the amount of electricity passed. The transport number was calculated from the equation:

$$t_+ = \frac{V.F.M}{Q} \quad (2)$$

where V denotes the volume in litres swept by the boundary, F is the Faraday in coulombs, M is the molarity of the nitric acid solution, and Q is the amount of electricity, in coulombs, passed through the cell. The transport number, calculated from equation (2), was then subjected to the solvent correction. The conductances of nitric acid solutions were measured at the required temperature and concentration. The correction was calculated from the formula⁸:

$$t_+ (\text{corr.}) = t_+ (\text{obs.}) \times \left(1 + \frac{k_{\text{solvent}}}{k_{\text{solution}}} \right) \quad \dots (3)$$

where k 's denote the specific conductances in the two cases. The correction for the volume changes at the electrodes was found to be insignificant and was therefore neglected.

Table I records the cationic transport numbers of nitric acid at five different concentrations and at various temperatures. The results at other concentrations have been omitted to economise space. Readings at higher concentrations than the last, mentioned in Table I, could not be taken on account of the marked diffusion at the boundary.

TABLE I

Conc. (moles/litre).	$\sqrt{C}$.	Cationic transport number t_+ of nitric acid at			
		25°.	30°.	40°.	50°.
0.00403	0.0635	0.8329	0.8293	0.8249	0.8202
0.02418	0.1550	0.8371	0.8434	0.8297	0.8257
0.04030	0.2008	0.8392	0.8361	0.8324	0.8279
0.06448	0.2539	..	..	0.8350	0.8306
0.08866	0.2978	0.8438	0.8404	0.8368	..

DISCUSSION

The plot of $\sqrt{C}$ against the transport number, t_+ , at a constant temperature is a straight line, as is clear from Fig. 1, in which the data at other concentrations, not recorded in Table I, have also been used.

8. Longworth, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2741.

By extrapolating the transport number t_+ vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves, for different temperatures, to zero concentration, one gets the limiting transport number, t_+^0 , for that temperature.

FIG. 1

The slope of the straight line is related to the corresponding equivalent conductance at infinite dilution, λ_0 , of the acid by the relation:

$$\text{Slope} = B_2 (2 t_+^0 - 1) / 2 \lambda_0 \quad (4)$$

B_2 being the constant given by

$$B_2 = \frac{825}{\eta (\epsilon T)^{0.5}}$$

where η is the viscosity, ϵ is the dielectric constant of the solvent, and T is the absolute temperature. One can use this relation to calculate λ_0 of the acid from the slope of t_+ vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curve for any desired temperature. In Table II are shown the limiting values of t_+ , obtained by extrapolation of t_+ vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves, and λ_0 as obtained from equation (4); then both of them have been compared with the already existing data.

TABLE II

Temp.	t_+^0 (from Fig. 1).	t_+^0 (from lit.).	λ_0 (eq. 4).	λ_0 (from lit.).
25°	0.8298	0.8304*	414	421.3
30°	0.8263	..	456	451.0**
40°	0.8218	..	507	512.0**
50°	0.8167	0.8172*	566	569.2

* Obtained from the relation $t_+^0 = \lambda_{0+}/\lambda_0$.

** Obtained from the plot of $\log \lambda_0$ vs. $1/T$ because the values at these temperatures are not given.

The agreement between the two sets of values of both t_+° and λ_+ appears to be satisfactory.

Effect of Temperature.—From Tables I and II it is clear that the cationic transport number of nitric acid decreases with rise in temperature. This is what is expected from the general considerations that the transport number greater than 0.5 should decrease with rise in temperature and should reach the limiting value of 0.5. If the ratio $\log(t_+^{\circ}/t_+^{\infty})$ for nitric acid between 0° and 50° is plotted against $1/T$, a straight line is obtained, as is shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

Similar curves are obtained in the cases of HCl, HBr, and HI and are also shown in Fig. 2. It appears therefore that the transport number in these acids are related to the absolute temperature, T , by the relation:

$$\log(t_+^{\circ}/t_+^{\infty}) = A + B/T$$

where A and B are constants for different acids.

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